

The Emotional Anatomy of Political Comedy

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Abstract

This article investigates the neurobiological and psychological underpinnings of political humor, positing that the divergence between liberal and conservative comedy is rooted in the interplay of brain structure, neuroplasticity, and affect theory. While early MRI studies (Kanai et al., 2011) suggested distinct anatomical differences between liberal (anterior cingulate cortex dominant) and conservative (amygdala dominant) brains, recent conflicting data (Petalas et al., 2024) suggests a more complex dynamic. This paper proposes that ideology functions as a form of lifelong entrainment—a self-directed neuroplastic training that reinforces specific emotional pathways.

Drawing on Silvan Tomkins' Affect Theory and Donald Nathanson's "Compass of Shame," the author argues that political humor is primarily a defense mechanism for managing cognitive shame and reinforcing tribal bonds. The essay contrasts the "humanistic" comedic style, which utilizes the ACC's tolerance for ambiguity and self-deprecation, with the "normative" style, which utilizes the amygdala's focus on threat detection and the "Attack Other" response. The 2011 White House Correspondents' Dinner involving Barack Obama and Donald Trump is analyzed as a collision of these neurological worldviews. Ultimately, the article warns that weaponized political humor acts as a behavioral addiction to revenge, hijacking the brain's reward circuitry and exacerbating polarization through the mechanism of humiliation.

Introduction

Is there a difference between conservative and liberal comedy in terms of human emotion? It's complicated, but the answer may be part of our biology. It's ultimately about how our worldview, or ideology, formed from our earliest experiences and reflected in our brain's structure and function, dominates our lives.

A Psychological and Neurological Framework

A 2011 MRI study by Kanai et al. first suggested that our political orientations may be literally embodied, finding that:

Greater liberalism was associated with increased gray matter in the anterior cingulate cortex (ACC), a brain region governing conflict monitoring and tolerance for ambiguity.

Greater conservatism was associated with an increased volume of the right amygdala, the brain's threat-detection center.

It would be nice if it were that simple. However, this finding has been challenged. A 2024 study by Petalas et al., using a larger sample, found no such statistical difference, leaving the direct link between brain anatomy and political affiliation unproven.

This is not a dead end; it is a clue. It suggests we may have been looking at the connection backward. The question might not be whether we are born with a "liberal" or "conservative" brain, but whether our brains can become more liberal or conservative in their functioning. Anatomy is not destiny. The error that we still make is thinking it is nature or nurture when it is clear it is both. Much of the evidence comes from a different field: psychotherapy.

Psychotherapy induces neuroplastic changes in key brain regions. The amygdala, central to fear and emotional reactivity, shows reduced hyperactivity and volume after therapies like CBT and exposure therapy, correlating with symptom improvement. The anterior cingulate cortex (ACC)—critical for emotion regulation—exhibits increased activation and gray matter volume post-treatment, particularly in mindfulness and CBT. Psychotherapy enhances connectivity between the ACC and prefrontal cortex (PFC), strengthening top-down control over the amygdala. These findings suggest therapy "rewires" emotional regulation networks, mirroring improvements in anxiety, depression, and PTSD.

To refine the nature vs. nurture thought we can see that in the average person nurture wins out as the evidence seems to point to humans having a stable base anatomy, think of the brain as hardware, a blank slate, that is then modified. Think of it as running our computer code of personally "scripted" or coded sets of affects- software (after Nathanson). I say the average person because there are many variations on base anatomy that do determine who we are. Genetic abnormalities such as Downs syndrome and Autism, for example, show anatomical brain changes from birth. Individuals with Superior Autobiographical Memory show enlarged temporal lobe/cingulate gyrus: Recalls daily life in cinematic detail (Neurocase, 2012). Synesthetes: Hyperconnected sensory cortices: Cross-wiring causes "colored hearing" (Journal of Neuroscience, 2016).

But staying with basic anatomy and focusing on the changes we can document from experience we have a bridge to politics and humor. An ideology is not just a set of beliefs; it is a lifelong framework for responding to the world. It is, in effect, a form of continuous, self-directed mental and emotional training. Therefore, I propose that the conflicting findings of Kanai and Petalas can be viewed through this lens of neuroplasticity. The differences the Kanai study may have detected might not be innate, but rather the result of a lifetime spent exercising specific neural pathways dictated by one's adopted worldview.

These physical structures modified throughout life-nature and nurture-provide a concrete basis for understanding how entrained neurology produces our thinking and behavior, a concept explored by psychologist Silvan Tomkins through his 'Polarity Scale,' which divides personalities into the flexible, communal humanist and the hierarchical, rule-bound normative. The normative (or authoritarian) paradigm suggests that human beings are born flawed and need to be made good through rules, discipline, and hierarchy.

The humanistic view, with roots in Greek thought, posits that we are born innocent and need to be nurtured. Life is a communal endeavor, and in this view, everyone is equal—the foundation of democracy.

The implications are profound once we combine all the findings. If so, the result can create an entrained neurobiological feedback loop. The ACC-dominant (liberal) brain seeks out cognitive dissonance, while the amygdala-driven (conservative) brain seeks to neutralize threats.

We recognize that the humanistic and normative attributes occur on a continuum. It is essential to note that Tomkins pointed out that most of us are a mixture of the two world views. This essay tends to highlight normative vs humanistic for didactic purposes. That said the idealized rigid forms do seem to be exemplified more starkly today in the real world.

These worldviews are not abstract philosophies adopted in adulthood; they are encoded in memory over a lifetime from our most powerful emotional responses through a subsequent layer of neurology, which Tomkins called affects. These can be seen as the basic components or elements of our software. An affect is the body's innate, physical response to a stimulus, occurring in milliseconds, before conscious thought. Tomkins named nine of these effects, which correspond to neural networks embedded in areas including the ACC and amygdala. These nine affects are: interest, joy, surprise, anger, fear, distress, disgust, dissmell (the affect of revulsion), and shame. Affects are not discrete areas in the brain. They tell us what is important and therefore are best seen as information networks that we can act on. This scares me, that angers me and I find something to be interesting. Within Tomkins' framework, the effect of Joy is often explained as the result of Interest building to Excitement, which is then resolved by the punchline—a sudden diminution of energy where laughter erupts.

These neural tools are ancient. Aristophanes' *The Clouds* weaponized disgust and dissmell to paint Socrates as a contaminant of Athenian youth—an amygdala-driven defense of tradition—while Molière's *Tartuffe* deployed irony (joy laced with anger) to expose religious hypocrisy, an ACC-guided strike at institutional deceit. The same affective 'software' has always powered political humor; only the cultural hardware updates.

Of the nine affects, the key effect for this discussion is shame. It is the universal feeling of hurt or confusion triggered by a sudden break in connection, as demonstrated powerfully in the "Still Face Experiment," where an infant displays profound distress when a caregiver suddenly becomes unresponsive. That interruption of the interest-joy bond is the purest form of shame.

That raw, biological interruption is the origin point of shame. As we grow from infancy into adulthood, we develop a lifetime of complex strategies, similar to ever evolving software, to cope with this primal feeling of hurt and disconnection. We turn the biological pain into a painful cognitive narrative. If we are raised in a normative household, that narrative can be "I am bad", I was told I was stupid. If it is a humanistic household the narrative will more likely be "Whatever happened is unfortunate, let's learn from it." These narratives we learn from others, and our own imagination, from our childhoods on.

Donald Nathanson, Silvan Tomkin's most prominent student, argued that many of our most ingrained behaviors are simply sophisticated ways of managing this core vulnerability of feeling cognitive shame as well as the nascent physical shame. Among the most powerful of these strategies is humor.

Nathanson found a perfect illustration of this in his encounter with the comedian Buddy Hackett, who revealed that his aggressive style was a classic case of shame avoidance. This is the "comic's paradox": that the biggest laughs often come from the deepest hurts. When this personal defense mechanism is scaled up to the political realm, the comedian isn't just managing their own shame; they are processing the collective anxiety and humiliation of an entire group. This exposes political humor's secret function: it is a form of shame alchemy, turning personal humiliation into tribal currency.

The Nature of Humor and Neural Warfare

Humor is a tool, and as we've seen, its use is dictated by our underlying neural architecture as well as our socialization. While it's possible to "attack the sin and not the sinner"—which should be the goal of the best humor - it is incredibly easy to slide into an ad hominem attack.

When President Obama's presumably liberal tendency to exercise his entrained ACC brain's crafted jokes to highlight the cognitive inconsistencies of birtherism (the idea that Obama was born in Kenya, and therefore not eligible to be president), it collided catastrophically with Donald Trump's presumably conditioned brain. An amygdala entrained on conservative values, threat detection, and the need to neutralize what it perceived as an existential threat. The event puts high-stakes political comedy in a new light, revealing it as a stage not just for wit, but for how neurology underpins who we are.

This is a powerful example of how those on the ideological divide can be misunderstood in their use of humor. In this case it may well be that Obama was being mean spirited and intentionally humiliating Trump, an ad hominem attack. On the other hand it could have all been meant to be in the time honored tradition of "Roasting", in this case an opponent. However roasting usually is with the at least tacit consent of the roasted.

At its best it can be seen as self deprecating humor by proxy. A call for Trump to "lighten up." You should know your target well to avoid actual humiliation. It highlights that all humor is at someone or something's expense and it can backfire. I remember when I saw it I felt uneasy. I immediately felt Obama had made a mistake both on the human level and political level.

We can go directly to the words of the participants to gain some understanding: Obama: "Maybe I should have taken it easy on him at the Correspondents' Dinner. But hey, he was right there in the front row—how could I resist?"

So, he is admitting to the opportunity to "attack" by saying "how could I resist?" He is tacitly admitting that Trump had "gotten to him in some way."

Meanwhile, Trump framed it as a defining moment of disrespect that fueled his political rise: "That's when I decided to run... I said, 'This country is going to hell.'"

Taken together, their statements paint a clear picture of the anterior cingulate cortex (ACC) meeting the right amygdala.

The episode underscores how humor in politics can misfire—especially when the target doesn't share the joke. While Obama saw it as playful ribbing, Trump took it as a personal slight, reinforcing his anti-establishment narrative. Whether the roast truly sparked his presidency or simply became a convenient origin story, it remains a pivotal moment in their rivalry.

To address an obvious objection, I am leaving aside the "radical" left and right in this analysis although it seems in the year 2025 we may be approaching having to deal with those extremes more. Nevertheless when ideologies become too extreme, their humor tends to decay into pure humiliation as they cannibalize each other.

Liberal Comedy: An ACC-Driven Expression

The liberal brain's entrainment of the ACC helps explain why its comedic style is psychologically elastic. There are demonstrably more liberal comedians because comedy's rebellious, boundary-pushing nature thrives on the cognitive flexibility and comfort with ambiguity that the ACC governs. At its best, this comedy uses interest and joy to target systems, fueled by a capacity for self-criticism (e.g., "I was stupid for saying that"). This is a hallmark of a well-functioning ACC strengthened through a lifetime of practiced openness to new experience.

It creates a communal dialectic that should foster solutions.

Conservative Comedy: An Amygdala-Driven Expression

The conservative stance, by contrast, is much more invested in rigid structures, a reflection of the amygdala's entrainment focusing it on stability and threat detection. This ideology is more brittle when challenged, and its humor is often reactive, engaging anger, distress, fear, disgust, and shame to target perceived threats to the social order. The humor of a show like *Gutfeld!* provides a conforming worldview that soothes the amygdala by reinforcing that "we" are safe and "they" are the danger. This focus on negative affects is no accident; our emotional toolbox is heavily biased toward them, with six carrying a negative valence versus only two positive (interest and joy), while surprise can go either way.

The Compass of Shame and the Addiction to Revenge

Donald Nathanson's "Compass of Shame" maps our four primary responses to the pain of a broken connection: Withdraw, Attack Self, Avoid, and Attack Other.

When we map our established neural tendencies onto the Compass, a clear political pattern emerges:

Humor that relies on ACC-dominant functions (common in liberalism) often uses the "Attack Self pole" (self-deprecation) or "Avoidance" (temporary relief from a known truth).

Amygdala-driven (Conservative) humor also uses avoidance (to protect an institution from a threatening truth) but more readily defaults to the "Attack Other" pole when that fails.

Another view of the neurological foundation of humor.

Deep in the brain, a pea-sized area processes threats. Since our first priority is survival, we have a built-in bias to more quickly reject than accept stimuli. This can be seen as a neurological "short circuit." My interest, grounded biologically in dopamine flow, is interrupted. When the flow of connection is interrupted, it is like an electrical current shorting out, it causes a moment of neurological pain which we have already mentioned as shame. I would claim that only then is this pain processed through the ACC and or amygdala. And only then do our learned behaviors kick in. This pea sized area is the habenula and is only fairly recently studied.

Revenge

Of the four negative shame responses the "Attack Other" is the engine of revenge. And we can certainly attack through humor. As research by James Kimmel Jr. shows, revenge is a behavioral addiction. Feeling shamed activates the brain's pain network; fantasizing about revenge activates the pleasure-and-reward circuitry, releasing dopamine. This is the neurology behind "cruelty is the point." The cruelty isn't random; it's the gratification of a neurologically ingrained addiction to neutralizing a threat—a severe "attack other" reaction.

If joy and laughter comes after interest - excitement (and excitement is seen as intense interest) it needs to be pointed out that in the revenge cycle the excitement component is as important as the pay off of joy. Excitement keeps the cycle going. Joy runs out of steam.

The laughter of an audience at the target's misfortune then serves as a powerful social reinforcer, deepening a vicious cycle that, in addiction terms, is incredibly hard to stop. As is the model for other addictions it is not first dopamine flow-> interruption of dopamine flow-> pain-> then resolution by solving the problem, but dopamine flow-> interruption of dopamine flow-> pain-> "Attack Other" which is fueled by hijacking the cycle of dopamine into a vicious cycle. Or in drug addiction: take more drugs to stimulate dopamine. In the healthy scenario there is resolution, in the unhealthy there is not.

We need to emphasize the result of "Attack Other" whether it be from humor or other means. But first an important clarification Attack Other in terms of the Compass of Shame is the encoded or scripted-automatic- response to emotional hurt. It is not the attack we need to use to survive although the two types will often be hard to separate. For certain humiliating an employee is not needed for the survival of the boss. Having made that distinction for our purposes in terms of humor it is, as we have pointed out, almost always at the expense of someone or something. If so then by definition it can harm. So either we are willing to take the chance that the other will get the joke or risk harm to the other. Here we go full circle back to the Obama-Trump encounter. More starkly how many people have been killed by someone so hurt by being laughed at that they return with a gun. Are we laughing with or at? In the professional realm Don Rickles was the master at a tightwire act of walking this line. I was never a fan of it. I am sure many of his targets did not take kindly to him.

In fact, political humor is so powerful precisely because it hijacks universal psychological mechanisms we use to navigate life in general. To see this mechanism stripped of its political charge, consider the humor of the Darwin Awards. Every year someone posts a list of people who have died doing something that most anyone would say was “stupid”.

Call it “dark” humor if you like. Most will, on the surface, think them funny. But what are we laughing at? It seems to me we are covering up the hurt we feel about the danger of being and acting human. “There for the grace of God go I.” On the other hand we might say “I would never do that.” Oh, but we all have come close, if we are honest with ourselves.

Justice, Forgiveness, and a Path Forward

If one has developed an addiction to revenge, and humor is a common vehicle by which to extract revenge, society often makes this addiction palatable by relabeling it as “justice.” This rebranding allows the revenge cycle to churn on a national scale, accelerated by social media. In terms of humor, ad hominem attacks are justified because the person “deserves” it.

Both the liberal brain and conservative brain, the addicted brain, can spiral out of control. As I mention, the extreme radical left and right end in cannibalizing each other and often themselves.

At a less extreme level can the spiral be stopped or treated? If revenge is a treatable addiction, then there is also a neurological antidote: forgiveness. Neuroscience shows that forgiving shuts down the brain’s pain network and reactivates our self-control. But this begs a question: if the “attack other” mode in humor or other areas, whether with a conservative or liberal bent, is in the realm of addiction, how do you bring anyone to forgiveness? That is a question I have no ready answer for. If Nathanson is right that humor works best when it acknowledges shame rather than weaponizes it, perhaps the healthiest political comedy would sound less like a roast and more like a recovery meeting.

Final Reflection

Ultimately, we must look under the hood. The humanist impulse is to understand, not to annihilate. Humiliating people is a dangerous game, as it triggers our hardwired instinct, whether liberal or conservative, to strike back. It is hubris to think our shaming will result in a quiet withdrawal; in the high-stakes game of politics, a counter-attack is to be expected. But how we use humor has consequences however we use it.

On a personal note, I have, for now, recently stopped listening to political humor. Much of what is happening is a horror, and I fear that humor now helps us avoid that horror instead of raising our consciousness. We must resist and protect our tribe, but shaming is not the way. Life is complicated, and we are not yet evolved enough to overcome our own emotional ignorance. But as we’ve seen, the science of shame—and its neurological roots—is coming to the fore. This is an exciting and necessary advance.

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